

Seed integration - a novel mechanism triggering cancer.

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Abstract

Bladder cancer in young women is rare and typically aggressive, with advanced cases linked to significant genomic instability. A recent case report by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025 described a 31-year-old woman developing stage IV bladder cancer within 12 months of receiving three doses of the Moderna modRNA COVID-19 vaccine. This study investigated potential molecular links between modRNA vaccination and oncogenesis, focusing on a 20 bp fragment from the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid Spike protein ORF (bases 5905–5924) integrated into chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674) of the patient's genome. Since multi-omic profiling revealed dysregulated oncogenic drivers (e.g., KRAS, PIK3CA) and impaired DNA repair mechanisms (e.g., ATM, MSH2) associated with the integrated fragment, we asked, if it is possible that such integrated fragment could carry sequence motif, enabling epigenetic mechanism of pro-oncogenic dysregulation. Using RNA22 v2 in this preliminary *in silico* analysis, we identified interactions between integrated 20 bp long fragment and tumor-suppressive hsa-let-7a-5p, hsa-miR-15a-5 microRNAs, indicating a possible “sponging” effect that could disrupt miRNA-mediated oncogene suppression. These findings further underscore the urgent need for rigorous “seed-proofreading” in all mRNA-based therapeutics to minimize unintended epigenetic effects, including microRNA dysregulation, inflammation, and cancer.

Key words: modRNA, bladder cancer, chromosome 19, microRNA, seed, COVID-19

Introduction:

Bladder cancer is predominantly a disease of older adults, with advanced cases in young women being exceptionally rare and typically aggressive [1, 12]. Concerns surround synthetic mRNA vaccines, which use modified mRNA (modRNA / mmRNA) and lipid nanoparticles (NLP), because unknown or not fully understood molecular mechanism associated with modRNA may potentially lead to genomic disruption, transcriptional dysregulation, and oncogenic activation due to residual plasmid DNA contamination, presence of nucleotide analogs, and likelihood of reverse transcription followed by genomic integration [4, 13, 5, 14]. A recent report by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025 presents the case of a 31-year-old woman developing stage IV bladder cancer within 12 months of receiving three doses of the Moderna modRNA COVID-19 vaccine [2]. The authors performed an in-depth molecular investigation to explore potential association with modRNA vaccination because such cases of advanced bladder cancer in young women and its aggressive presentation are typically very rare phenomena. The study utilized advanced multi-omic profiling techniques, including PBIMA (Molecular Surveillance and Individualized Targeted Immunotherapy Peptide Editing) and REViSS (Spike-associated Transcriptional/Translational Instability Surveillance), to analyze plasma-derived circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), whole-blood RNA, and urine exosome proteom. The findings revealed

dysregulated oncogenic driver genes (e.g., KRAS, ATM, MAPK1, NRAS, CHD4, PIK3CA, SF3B1), auxiliary tumor-promoting signals (e.g., TOP1, PSIP1, ERBB2), and impaired DNA repair mechanisms (e.g., ATM, MSH2), indicating significant genomic instability [2, 3, 15]. A critical discovery was a host–vector chimeric read in ctDNA, mapping to chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674, GRCh38) in cytoband 19q13.42, which aligned with perfect 20/20 bp identity to a segment of the Spike protein Open Reading Frame (ORF) in the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid (bases 5905–5924, GenBank: OR134577.1), despite the patient receiving Moderna vaccines only. This alignment, statistically unlikely to be random (1 in a trillion probability), suggests integration of vaccine-derived genetic material into the patient's genome. The integration site, located outside the AAVS1 safe harbor [16] in a gene-dense, recombination-prone region near the zinc-finger (ZNF) gene cluster [17, 18], suggests potential for transcriptional disruption and oncogenic transformation. MicroRNA (miRNA / miR) are small, ~22 nucleotide non-coding RNAs that function as pivotal post-transcriptional regulators of gene expression, influencing virtually all critical biological processes, including immune response, cell cycle control, differentiation, and apoptosis [19]. They typically bind to complementary sequences in the 3' untranslated regions (UTRs) of target messenger RNA (mRNA), primarily through a 6-8 nucleotide "seed region" (positions 2-8 of miRNA), leading to translational repression and mRNA degradation [20]. Particularly significant is the role of miRs in oncogenesis, where they function as key tumor suppressors (TS-miRNAs) or onco-miRs promoting cancer. TS-miRNAs, such as those belonging to the let-7, miR-15 or miR-34 families, are often down-regulated in cancer cells since their primary function is to inhibit the expression of powerful oncogenes, such as KRAS (a target of let-7) [21, 22], BCL2 (a target of miR-15/16 or miR-34a) [23, 36], or MYC (also a target of the let-7 family of miRs) [21, 24], thereby inducing apoptosis, inhibiting proliferation, and maintaining control of the cell cycle [21, 23, 24, 25]. The loss of function of these miRs leads therefore to derepression of oncogenic pathways and promotes cellular transformation [26]. On the other hand, onco-miRs (e.g., miR-21, miR-155) are often over-expressed in cancers and promote tumorigenesis by down-regulating tumor suppressor genes, such as for instance PTEN [27, 28]. Our recent study Kukier *et al.* 2025 provided initial *in silico* evidence that both the SARS-CoV-2 genome and modRNA-based COVID-19 vaccines contain conserved "seed" binding sites for the tumor-suppressive hsa-miR-143-5p [29]. This finding suggested that exogenous modRNA could act as a molecular „sponge“, sequestering cellular microRNAs and potentially dysregulating their native function in inflammation and oncogenesis [10, 11]. In this current report, we analyse whether selected TS-miRs have their "seed" motifs within the 20 bp fragment of the Spike protein Open Reading Frame (ORF) from the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid (bases 5905–5924, GenBank: OR134577.1) found by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025 to be integrated within chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674, GRCh38), cytoband 19q13.42 of the patient developing stage IV bladder cancer within 12 months of receiving three doses of the Moderna mRNA COVID-19 vaccine [2].

Material and Methods

We used Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 sequence (GenBank: OR134577.1) available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/OR134577.1> in which the 20 bp long fragment found to be integrated with the chromosome 19, corresponds to bases 5905–5924 of Spike protein ORF in the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid (CDS: 3674..7480n bp / protein_id = WIW57999.1). The sequence of this fragment is following: [CTCCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGT]. For more precise analysis this 20 bp fragment was flanked by the 15 bp

long sequences on its 5' and 3' end, corresponding to the adequate sequences within the Spike protein ORF of the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid. The final sequence for our *in silico* analysis had therefore the following sequence: CGATTCCACCGAGTG-5905-[CTCCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGT]-5924-ACGGCAGCTTCTGCA. For the analysis of the interaction between this 20 bp long Spike protein fragment and microRNAs, we used RNA22 v2 algorithm available at: <https://cm.jefferson.edu/rna22/Interactive>. RNA22 v2 predicts miRNA-mRNA interactions based on intrinsic sequence complementarity, thermodynamic stability (free energy, ΔG) and statistical significance (p-value), independent on the evolutionary conservation. This approach captures high-affinity binding potential that may be mediated by non-canonical interactions or stabilized by non-canonical 3'-end pairing, a major determinant of the specificity with the Argonaute complex interaction [13, 17]. The ΔG was considered as the primary filter for high-confidence interactions. The sequences of miRs analysed in this report were obtained from the miRBase - microRNA database (<https://www.mirbase.org>), which is the major archive for microRNA sequences and annotations. The following miRs were analysed:

hsa-let-7a-5p / UGAGGUAGUAGGUUGUAUAGUU

hsa-miR-15a-5p / UAGCAGCACAUAAUGGUUUGUG

hsa-miR-15b-5p / UAGCAGCACAUCAUGGUUACA

hsa-miR-98-5p / UGAGGUAGUAAGUUGUAUUGUU

Results

The RNA22 v2 analysis returned positive results with three of the four tested miRs. hsa-miR-98-5p did not produce any significant interaction under various conditions applied in our analysis even though a weak interaction is present when the complete sequence of the Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 is tested (Data not shown but available in [Supplementary Data - S1](#)). Table 1 presents the results obtained for three other miRs.

Table 1. [Tab_1_RNA22v2_heteroduplex_Kukier et al. 2025 (4)]

Furthermore, we did run a BLASTn (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) between the complete sequence of Pfizer bivalent expression vector BNT162b2 (OR134577.1) and the complete sequence of ModeRNA mRNA1273 expression vector (OR134578.1) to verify the level of overall identity between these sequences with special emphasis on the identity within the 20 bp long fragment [CTCCAACCTGCTGCTGCAGT], corresponding to the bases 5905–5924 of the Spike protein ORF in Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid as stated above. Figure. 1 indicates that both sequences of the Pfizer and ModeRNA expression vectors show significant identity within the region containing 20 bp long fragment found to be integrated with chromosome 19 in patient with stage IV bladder cancer. The entire BLASTn result is available in [Supplementary Data - S2](#).

Fig. 1. [Fig_1_BLASTn_Pf_Mod_Kukier et al. 2025 (4)]

These results further highlight what previous studies indicated, namely that the likelihood for the modRNA of both COVID-19 vaccines (Pfizer and ModeRNA) and thus most likely any modRNA-based therapeutics

to be reverse-transcribed and integrated with the genomic, chromosomal DNA is significant and cannot be dismissed [4, 5, 6].

Discussion

In this preliminary analysis, we sought to verify whether an interaction is possible between tumor-suppressing microRNAs (TS-miRs) and the 20 bp long fragment, found to be integrated within chromosome 19 (chr19:55,482,637–55,482,674, GRCh38), cytoband 19q13.42 of a patient developing stage IV bladder cancer as reported recently by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025 [2]. Our results clearly indicate a possibility for such an interaction between three out of four tested TS-miRs with the 20 bp long fragment, corresponding to the Spike protein Open Reading Frame (ORF) from the Pfizer BNT162b2 plasmid (bases 5905–5924, GenBank: OR134577.1). The fact that this 20 bp long sequence, identical to the corresponding sequence in Pfizer BNT162b2, was obtained from a patient with stage IV bladder cancer developing within 12 months of receiving three doses of the Moderna mRNA COVID-19 vaccine only, can most likely be explained by the fact that both expression vectors are 90% identical within this 20 bp long sequence as was confirmed by our BLASTn analysis (Fig. 1). It is therefore possible that both COVID-19 vaccine modRNAs undergo selective reverse transcription, most likely carried out by LINE-1 activity [4, 33]. However, it is also possible that the source of this 20 bp long fragment integrated with chromosome 19 of the patient originated from the plasmid DNA fragments contaminating modRNA vaccine(s) as detected previously by McKernan *et al.* 2023 and others [7, 8]. The role of miRNAs in inflammation and oncogenesis is well established [19, 26]. These RNA molecules function as key tumor suppressors (TS-miRNAs) as well as onco-miRs promoting cancer progression. One example of such tumor-suppressive type of miRs is the let-7 family - often down-regulated in many cells at very early stages of cancer [21, 34]. The primary function of such TS-miRs is to epigenetically suppress, at the level of mRNA, the expression of early oncogenes, such as e.g. KRAS and MYC - both targets of the let-7 family of miRs [21, 22, 24] or BCL2 - a target of the miR-15 family of miRs [23], thereby inducing apoptosis, inhibiting proliferation, and maintaining control of the cell cycle [21, 23, 24, 25]. The loss of function of these TS-miRs leads therefore to de-repression of oncogenic pathways and results in much higher probability of cellular oncogenic transformation [26]. Recent studies have also revealed that microRNA targeting rules are more complex than previously anticipated. While canonical "seed" pairing at the 5'-end of a miR remains crucial, the miR's 3'-end pairing and non-canonical interactions significantly contribute to the binding specificity and stability of the miR-mRNA heteroduplex on the Argonaute/RISC complex, as was demonstrated by the microRNA-chimeras from endogenous Argonaute-bound RNAs [30, 31, 35]. These findings are particularly relevant when considering potential off-target effects of exogenous RNA sequences, such as those of viruses or modRNA-based therapeutics. In our analysis, we could see that hsa-miR-let7a-5p has more favourable pairing towards its 3'-end within the 20 bp long fragment of modRNA vaccine (Table.1). If indeed true, this could indicate its stronger interaction with the Ago/RISC complex. On the other hand, hsa-miR-15a-5p and hsa-miR-15b-5p seem to form a canonical 7mer at the perfect "seed" motif embedded in the 20 bp long fragment of COVID-19 vaccine modRNAs from Pfizer. This result applies also to ModeRNA COVID-19 vaccine modRNA since our BLASTn alignment clearly shows a 100% identity of both sequences within this 20 bp long fragment, preserving the microRNA 7mer „seed’ motif (Fig.1). This highlights a possibility for an efficient "sponging" effect of tumor-suppressor microRNAs tested in our analysis [10, 11]. Such a sponging effect, exercised by modRNA

itself upon entry into the cell or by its transcripts if reverse transcribed and integrated into the genomic DNA, could lead to a significant increase in the probability of oncogenesis due to the dysregulation of the microRNA network, responsible for suppressing oncogenes by the mechanism of down-regulating their mRNAs. This microRNA "sponging" effect (similar to the role of some circRNAs) would be especially concerning in the case of modRNA sequence integration within a chromosomal region of higher transcriptional activity, especially if the integration site is located within a gene-dense, recombination-prone region near the zinc-finger (ZNF) gene cluster known to be constitutively transcribed [17, 18] as it seems to be the case reported by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025 [2]. Nevertheless, even though our analysis resulted in what seems to be a perfect heteroduplex formation between hsa-miR-15a-5p and has-miR-15b-5p at the canonical 7mer "seed" sequence contained within the 20 bp long fragment of COVID-19 vaccine modRNAs, the p-value calculated by the RNA22v2 application for these miRs appears to undermine our results. A p-value of $2.31e-1$ (0.231) means that there is approximately a 23% probability of observing a result similar to the one obtained in the study, assuming the null hypothesis (miR interaction via "seed" sequence with 20 bp modRNA fragment) is true. Such a value is far from the statistically significant threshold of 0.05, and hence these results may be considered a weak evidence against the null hypothesis, leading to the conclusion of their statistical insignificance. However, we must take to consideration that results obtained *in silico* studies, represent only an approximation of a well established general molecular mechanisms, which do occur within the cell with high probability and as such our findings do require a more in-depth analysis and most of all - experimental verification. The interaction between miRs and mRNA may be influenced *in vivo* by a myriad of circumstances such as pH, methylation, pseudouridylation, and even RNA-glycosylation - all exerting a drastic modulatory effect, which could increase or decrease the likelihood and stability of interaction. These results must be therefore experimentally verified and perceived as a strong suggestion that a legally obligatory introduction of a modRNA "seed-proofreading" approach at the very designing phase of every modRNA-based therapeutic must be urgently introduced to minimize the chance for interaction of such therapeutics with the cellular microRNAs regulatory network. This strategy is absolutely necessary to reduce the mechanistic risk of unintended epigenetic side effects, including microRNA-dependent inflammation and cancer [29].

Supplementary Data

[Supplementary data - S1](#)

[Supplementary data - S2](#)

Additional information

This article was developed with the support of artificial intelligence, namely Grok by @xAI (<https://x.ai>). While we strive for accuracy, some minor errors may still persist. The idea that a particular group of tumor-suppressing microRNAs may interact with 20 bp long fragment of the Pfizer (and Moderna) COVID-19 vaccine modRNAs (as published by Catanzaro *et al.* 2025) is our original contribution.

Author Contribution

All authors listed have made intellectual and direct contributions to this work and approved it for publication.

Conflict of Interest

The authors listed declare that this work was conducted in the absence of any relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Funding

The authors declare that no funding was received for this work.

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